

1 **A first Chinese building height estimate at 10 m**
2 **resolution (CNBH-10m) using multi-source earth**
3 **observations and machine learning**

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21 **Highlights:**

- 22 ● The first country-wide 10 m building height map for China
23 ● Shading index is the most important variable in estimating building height
24 ● High degree of building height accuracy with RMSE of 6.1 m

25

26 **Abstract**

27 Building height is a crucial variable in the study of urban environments, regional
28 climates, and human-environment interactions. However, high-resolution data on
29 building height, especially at the national scale, are limited. Fortunately, high spatial-
30 temporal resolution earth observations, harnessed using a cloud-based platform, offer
31 an opportunity to fill this gap. We describe an approach to estimate 2020 building height
32 for China at 10 m spatial resolution based on all-weather earth observations (radar,
33 optical, and night light images) using the Random Forest (RF) model. Results show that
34 our building height simulation has a strong correlation with real observations at the
35 national scale (RMSE of 6.1 m, MAE=5.2 m, R=0.77). The Combinational Shadow
36 Index (CSI) is the most important contributor (15.1%) to building height simulation.
37 Analysis of the distribution of building morphology reveals significant differences in
38 building volume and average building height at the city scale across China. Macau has
39 the tallest buildings (22.3 m) among Chinese cities, while Shanghai has the largest
40 building volume ($298.4 \times 10^8 \text{ m}^3$). The strong correlation between modelled building
41 volume and socio-economic parameters indicates the potential application of building
42 height products. The building height map developed in this study with a resolution of
43 10 m is open access, provides insights into the 3D morphological characteristics of
44 cities and serves as an important contribution to future urban studies in China.

45 **Keywords:** Multi-Sensor; Machine learning; Urban morphology; Google Earth
46 Engine; Building height

47

48 **1. Introduction**

49 Accurate measurement of building height is essential for understanding the
50 impacts of urbanization on the urban environment. Building height is correlated with
51 urban energy use (Resch et al. 2016), greenhouse gas emissions (Borck 2016;
52 Marconcini et al. 2020) and human wellbeing (Liang et al. 2020; Schug et al. 2021).
53 Furthermore, it is a crucial variable in volumetric analysis (Sun et al. 2018), population
54 mapping (Alahmadi et al. 2013) and living conditions such as *per capita* space
55 availability (Ghosh et al. 2020). Building height also has a significant impact on urban
56 climate (Xi et al. 2021), including urban heat islands effects (Huang and Wang 2019;
57 Perini and Magliocco 2014; Wu et al. 2022), solar radiation (Cheng et al. 2020;
58 Sorichetta et al. 2015) and wind speeds (Miao et al., 2009). Accurate mapping of
59 building height is therefore an important basis in improving our understanding of urban
60 processes.

61 In recent decades, two-dimensional (2D) urban morphology, including urban
62 boundaries, the extent of impervious surface, and human settlement footprints, have
63 received considerable attention and resulted in many high-resolution and global
64 products (Gong et al. 2020; Li et al. 2020b; Marconcini et al. 2020; Mertes et al. 2015).
65 There are, however, relatively few studies or products available for three-dimensional
66 (3D) urban structures, and most of these focus on particular cities with spatial resolution
67 limited to 0.3-1km (Kedron et al. 2019; Li et al. 2020c; Yang and Zhao 2022; Zhang et
68 al. 2018). Even scarcer are 3D high-resolution data for urban structures in large and
69 connected areas (Zhu et al. 2019).

70 Currently, open-source and freely available earth observations are widely used for
71 3D mapping of urban morphology. For example, using Sentinel-1 backscatter data, Li
72 et al. (2020c) modelled building height at 500 m spatial resolution for major cities in
73 the US. Yang and Zhao (2022) presented a building height map for China at 1km-
74 spatial-resolution based on Sentinel-1 data and spatially-informed Gaussian process

75 regression. However, the accuracy and application of such models is constrained by the
76 backward scattering coefficient which is influenced not only by building height but also
77 by the surface characteristics of construction materials, the composition of land-cover
78 surrounding the buildings, and by the roughness characteristics of buildings or trees
79 (Koppel et al. 2017; Vreugdenhil et al. 2018). It is possible to address these limitations,
80 Huang et al. (2022), developed a method to estimate building height for China based
81 on the Advanced Land Observing Satellite (ALOS) World 3D-30 m (AW3D30) DSM
82 (Huang et al. 2022). As illustrated by Frantz et al. (2021), who combined Sentinel-1A/B
83 and Sentinel-2A/B time series data to construct a model of building height for the whole
84 of Germany. However, China has a more complex urban 3D structure, greater degree
85 of building heterogeneity, and a wider distribution of high-rise buildings (Li et al. 2020a)
86 and accordingly the method requires further modification to produce a reliable estimate
87 building height at the national scale.

88 An accurate map of building height is a basic requirement to support urban
89 environmental research and planning, the more so in China with its prolific and rapid
90 scale of urbanization. To date, however, there is no high resolution (less than 30 m)
91 map of building height on a national scale. In filling this research gap, this study aims
92 to develop a first Chinese building height map at 10 m resolution (CNBH-10 m) based
93 on data from an open-source earth observation platform analysed using machine
94 learning. The main research objectives of the study are as follows:

95 (1) To construct high-resolution building height estimation models using data from
96 multiple-source, multi-temporal, and multi-scale to accommodate complex urban
97 structures at the national scale in China.

98 (2) To evaluate the accuracy and generalizability of building height models in
99 different regions of the country.

100 (3) To explore the distribution of different building forms in China and the factors
101 underlying this distribution.

102 2. Data Description

103 2.1 Independent variables

104 As summarized in Table 1, the independent variables used to estimate building
105 height include radar data, optical data, night-time light data, population data,
106 topographic data, and settlement distribution data. Each variable and preprocessing step
107 is described in detail below. We did not filter the variables for further regression
108 because the RF model is insensitive to multivariate linearity (Breiman 2001).

109 2.1.1 Sentinel-1

110 Sentinel-1 Ground Range Detected (GRD) scenes were used to estimate urban
111 building height which provides data from a dual-polarization C-band Synthetic
112 Aperture Radar (SAR) instrument. Sentinel-1 imageries are available at 10 m resolution
113 and a short revisit time (6-12 days) (Dai et al. 2016). In this study, two polarization
114 bands, VV and VH, and dual-polarization information derived VVH (Li et al. 2020c)
115 were used for further building height estimation. All Sentinel-1 SAR GRD data are
116 available on the GEE platform (Gorelick et al. 2017), and all the data on GEE were
117 processed using Sentinel-1 Toolbox (Veci et al. 2014) to generate a calibrated, ortho-
118 corrected product. A total of 56,821 scenes of Sentinel-1 data were used in this study.
119 Fig. 1a shows the total observations of Sentinel-1 data from 2019 to 2021.

120 The dual-polarised information derived VVH was calculated as follows:

$$121 \quad VVH = VV * \gamma^{VH} \quad (1.)$$

122 Where γ was set to 5 based on a former study (Li et al. 2020c).

123 2.1.2 PALSAR

124 Phased Array Type L-band Synthetic Aperture Radar (PALSAR) is an active
125 microwave sensor which has a multi-polarization configuration, and is widely used for
126 the estimation of vertical structure in vegetation. In this study, global 25 m PALSAR/

127 PALSAR-2 yearly mosaic data from 2019 to 2021 were obtained from the GEE data
 128 catalog (Collection Snippet: "JAXA/ALOS/PALSAR/YEARLY/SAR"). To ensure
 129 high-quality data, the SAR images with the lowest response to surface moisture were
 130 prefer used for creating the annual product using the mean composite method (Shimada
 131 et al. 2014).

132 2.1.3 Sentinel-2

133 In this study, a total of 160,023 scenes of Sentinel-2 were utilized. The QA60
 134 bitmask band was used to mask out poor-quality observations caused by clouds (Bit 10)
 135 and cirrus clouds (Bit 11) (Ni et al. 2021) for each image. Fig. 1b shows the total number
 136 of cloud free observations of Sentinel-2 data during 2019 to 2021. In addition to
 137 Sentinel-2 bands, six other spectral indices were considered as independent variables,
 138 including Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) (Pettorelli 2013; Tucker
 139 1979), Enhanced Vegetation Index (EVI) (Huete et al. 2002), Land Surface Water Index
 140 (LSWI) (Xiao et al. 2004), Modified Normalized Difference Water Index (MNDWI)
 141 (Xu 2006), Normalized Difference Built-up Index (NDBI) (Zha et al. 2003), and
 142 Combinational Shadow Index (CSI) (Sun et al. 2019). Equations used to calculate the
 143 indices are as follows:

$$144 \quad NDVI = \frac{\rho_{NIR} - \rho_{red}}{\rho_{NIR} + \rho_{red}} \quad (2.)$$

$$145 \quad EVI = \frac{2.5(\rho_{NIR} - \rho_{red})}{(\rho_{NIR} + 6\rho_{red} - 7.5\rho_{blue} + 1)} \quad (3.)$$

$$146 \quad LSWI = \frac{\rho_{NIR} - \rho_{swir1}}{\rho_{NIR} + \rho_{swir1}} \quad (4.)$$

$$147 \quad MNDWI = \frac{\rho_{green} - \rho_{swir1}}{\rho_{green} + \rho_{swir1}} \quad (5.)$$

$$148 \quad NDBI = \frac{\rho_{swir1} - \rho_{NIR}}{\rho_{swir1} + \rho_{NIR}} \quad (6.)$$

$$149 \quad SEI = \frac{(\rho_{aerosols} + \rho_{water\ vapor}) - (\rho_{green} + \rho_{NIR})}{(\rho_{aerosols} + \rho_{water\ vapor}) + (\rho_{green} + \rho_{NIR})} \quad (7.)$$

$$150 \quad CSI = \begin{cases} SEI - \rho_{NIR}, & \text{if } \rho_{NIR} \geq NDWI \\ SEI - NDWI, & \text{else} \end{cases} \quad (8.)$$

151 where ρ_{red} , ρ_{green} , ρ_{blue} , ρ_{NIR} , ρ_{swir1} , $\rho_{aerosols}$, $\rho_{water\ vapor}$ are the surface
152 reflectance of the red, green, blue, near infrared, shortwave infrared, aerosols and water
153 vapor bands of the Sentinel-2 MSI sensor.

154 2.1.4 LUOJIA night light image

155 LUOJIA 1-01, a new nighttime light (NTL) data satellite launched by China in 2018,
156 has a spatial resolution of 130 meters (Li et al. 2018). In this investigation, we utilized
157 LUOJIA night light images from 2018 as input data to derive estimations of building
158 heights. To improve the accuracy of NTL, we calculated the Vegetation Adjusted NTL
159 Urban Index (VANUI) (Zhang et al. 2013) based on *equation 9* to mitigate the
160 oversaturation effect of NTL.

$$161 \quad VANUI = (1 - NDVI) * NTL \quad (9.)$$

162 where NDVI is the annual mean NDVI derived from Landsat products in 2018 and
163 NTL is the DN value of LUOJIA 1-01 NTL data.

164 2.1.5 Settlement footprint

165 The World Settlement Footprint (WSF) layer for 2019 is a global human settlement
166 distribution product at a ground resolution of 10 m derived from Landsat-8 and
167 Sentinel-1 data. In this study, the settlement coverage derived from WSF 2019 was
168 extracted as an independent variable for building height estimation and was also used
169 to mask the final CNBH-10m product to remove to remove non-built-up pixels. We
170 chose WSF due to its superior ability to remove roads between buildings, as well as its
171 high user accuracy and accuracy of area estimation compared to other datasets such as
172 ESA WorldCover, ESRI Land Cover, and GHS-BUILT-S2 (Wang et al. 2022). Fig. 1c
173 shows the distribution of WSF in 2019.

174 2.1.6 Other independent variables

175 Considering the large extent of mainland China's latitude and longitude range, from
176 73°33'E to 135°05'E and from 3°51'N to 53°33'N, we incorporated the potential impact
177 of variations in solar elevation angle on the model in our selection of variables for
178 building height inversion. We included building location (longitude and latitude) and
179 topographic information (DEM and slope) as key variables, as these factors
180 significantly affect the solar elevation angle. In addition, population size was
181 considered as an independent variable. More detailed information on the data sets used
182 here is presented in Table 1. All variables were resampled to 10 m using the nearest
183 neighbor resampling method for building height modeling and estimation.

184 2.2 Reference building height dataset

185 The vector building footprint data, which incorporate the information relating to the
186 number of floors for 62 cities in China for the year 2018 (Fig. 1d) were collected from
187 Baidu map services (<http://www.map.baidu.com>). To obtain the building height for
188 each building, the number of building floors was multiplied by 3 m (Tripathy et al. 2022;
189 Wu et al. 2022). Liu et al. (2021) report an accuracy of 86.8%, with a mean height
190 deviation of approx. 1 m, for this dataset. In order to acquire sample points of building
191 footprint for further analysis, we used the method (equation 10) from Frantz et al. (2021)
192 to convert the vector building height data of single buildings to 10 m spatial resolution
193 grid data. In order to enhance the quality of samples and mitigate errors arising from
194 incomplete building measurements, the analysis excluded samples within a 50-meter
195 radius of the sampling point that exhibited a difference of more than 25% between the
196 building footprint vector data and the WSF building distribution in terms of area. In this
197 study, a total of 22,909 samples were used to train (70%) and validate (30%) the
198 building height model.

$$199 \quad BH_{10m} = \frac{\sum_p^n H_p * A_p}{\sum_p^n A_p}$$

200 (10.)

201 where H_p and A_p represent the height and area of individual building patches,
 202 respectively, while $\sum_p^n A_p$ denotes the total area of all building patches within the
 203 statistical area.

204

205 Fig. 1 Study area and data availability. (a) number of Sentinel-1 observations from 2019
 206 to 2021; (b) number of cloud free Sentinel-2 observations from 2019 to 2021; (c) human
 207 settlement footprint of China in 2019; (d) reference building height data distribution
 208 (colored polygon).

209 Table 1. Datasets used to estimate building height

Code	Products	Variables	Acquisition time	Resolution	Data Source	Reference
0	Reference building height	building height	2019	Vector	http://www.map.baidu.com	(Liu et al. 2021)
1-3	Sentinel-1	VV; VH; VVH	2019-2021	10 m	" COPERNICUS/S1_GRD " (Collection Snippet in GEE)	(Torres et al. 2012)
4-5	PALSAR	HH; HV	2019-2021	25 m	" JAXA/ALOS/PALSAR/YEARLY/SAR " (Collection Snippet in GEE)	(Shimada et al. 2014)
6-22	Sentinel-2	Aerosols; Blue; Green; Red; NIR; Red Edge 1-4; SWIR 1; SWIR 2; NDVI; EVI; LSWI; MNDWI; NDBI; CSI	2019-2021	10/20/60 m	" COPERNICUS/S2_SR " (Collection Snippet in GEE)	(Drusch et al. 2012)
23	LUOJIA 1-01	VANUI	2018	130 m	http://www.hbeos.org.cn	(Li et al. 2018)
24	World population	Population	2020	100 m	" WorldPop/GP/100 m/pop " (Collection Snippet in GEE)	(Sorichetta et al. 2015)
25-26	SRTM	DEM; Slope	2000	90 m	https://srtm.csi.cgiar.org	(Rodriguez et al. 2006)
27	WSF 2019	Settlement coverage	2019	10 m	https://geoservice.dlr.de/web/maps/eoc:wsf2019	(Marconcini et al. 2020)
28-29	Location	Latitude; Longitude	/	10 m	/	/

210

211 3. Methodology

212 Fig. 2 illustrates the workflow developed for the building height estimation based
 213 on multi-source, multi-temporal, all-weather earth observations. The approach consists
 214 of three main sections. First, the preprocessing of independent variables was conducted
 215 by combining multi-temporal, multi-spectral, multi-window, and multi-statistical
 216 methods. Second, the Random Forest (RF) model was used to construct and optimize
 217 the estimation model. Third, the validation of the simulations was referenced against
 218 real building height data.

220 **Fig. 2** Method overview of CNBH-10 m estimation

221 3.1 Preparation of variables

222 All Sentinel-1 and cloud free Sentinel-2 time series were temporally aggregated to
 223 enhance the richness of information. This processing step employed the spectral-
 224 temporal variability approach (Frantz et al. 2021). We calculated the maximum,
 225 minimum, and standard deviation of the time series of Sentinel-1, Sentinel-2, and their
 226 derivatives variables for the three-year period from 2019 to 2021. To capture shadow
 227 features across different levels of building heights, we employed multi-window local
 228 statistics (Figure 3) that utilized both spectral features and radar data. We applied

229 maximum and mean statistical methods to circles with radii of 50 m, 100 m, 150 m, and
230 200 m.

231

232 **Fig. 3 Method of multi-window statistics**

233 3.2 Building height model

234 The RF regression model (Liaw and Wiener 2002) was used to estimate building
235 height, where a total of 519 variables were set as predictors, and 22,909 samples were
236 used as training samples. The number of trees (Ntree) and the number of features
237 randomly selected to split each node (Mtry) are two crucial parameters of the RF model.
238 Increasing Ntree can enhance the performance of random forests. Since the RF
239 classifier is computationally efficient and non-overfitting, Ntree can be set to the
240 highest feasible value (Guan et al. 2013). In most of the studies reviewed here, the Ntree
241 value was set at 500, as the errors of the classification tree stabilize before this number
242 is reached (Lawrence et al. 2006). When Mtry is small, the model's variance decreases,
243 but the bias increases, as some critical features may be ignored. When Mtry is large,
244 the variance of the model increases, but the bias decreases as the model considers more
245 features. Previous research suggests using the square root of the number of variables as
246 the value for Mtry (Gislason et al. 2006). Therefore, in this study, we set Ntree and
247 Mtry to 600 and the square root of the number of variables, respectively. In order to
248 understand the importance of different variables for the building height model, the
249 relative importance of each variable was evaluated using the Mean Decrease in Gini

250 (MDG) method (Breiman 2001). For 2019, WSF data were used to define the settlement
 251 footprint of the CNBH-10 m map. The RF regression model was performed on the
 252 Google Earth Engine (GEE) platform (Gorelick et al. 2017).

253 3.3 Accuracy assessment

254 To assess the accuracy of the estimated building height, three indicators were
 255 calculated including R, Root Mean Square error (RMSE) and Mean Absolute Error
 256 (MAE) based on 30% of the reference samples. In this study, we evaluated the accuracy
 257 of the model using both the least squares (LS) regression model and the weighted least
 258 squares (WLS) regression model. The WLS model assigns weights to each building
 259 height category, with data points appearing more frequently in the height category
 260 having a lower weight, resulting in a more precise estimation of the slope of the
 261 regression line.

$$262 \quad R = \sqrt{1 - \frac{(n-1) \sum_{i=1}^n (BH_{est,i} - BH_{ref,i})^2}{(n-2) \sum_{i=1}^n (BH_{est,i} - BH_{ref,i})^2}} \quad (11.)$$

$$263 \quad RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (BH_{est,i} - BH_{ref,i})^2}{n}} \quad (12.)$$

$$264 \quad MAE = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n |BH_{est,i} - BH_{ref,i}|}{n} \quad (13.)$$

265 where n is the number of validation samples, $BH_{est,i}$ is the estimated building height
 266 value, and $BH_{ref,i}$ is the reference building height value.

267 4. Results

268 4.1 Relative importance of variables

269 Fig. 4 illustrates the relative importance of each independent variable in the
 270 building height estimation model. The cumulative relative importance (Fig. 4 a)
 271 indicates that the CSI makes the largest contribution (15.1%) to the estimation model,
 272 followed by VH (7.8%). Overall, the contribution of optical, radar, and other data to
 273 the building height estimation model is 76.6%, 18.2%, and 5.3%, respectively.

274 According to the average degree of importance of each independent variable (Fig. 4 b),
 275 building location (latitude, longitude, DEM, slope), and settlement density also
 276 contribute to the simulation, albeit less so. The importance of information gathered by
 277 windows of different sizes varies for building height models, as the relative importance
 278 of the 50 m, 100 m, 150 m, and 200 m scales are 34.2%, 32.5%, 22.4%, and 5.6%,
 279 respectively. To summarize, optical information exhibits the highest level of
 280 importance in combination with the most significant scales of 50 and 100 m.

281

282 **Fig. 4.** (a) Cumulative and (b) average relative importance of each variable under
 283 various spatial-temporal fusion methods

284 The results in Figure 5 show the progression of estimation accuracy as the number
 285 of variables increases. A total of 519 models were constructed by incrementally adding
 286 variables based on their relative importance, and the change in model accuracy was
 287 assessed as the number of independent variables increased. The results indicate that the
 288 inclusion of a certain number of variables significantly improves estimation accuracy,
 289 but that further increasing the number of variables eventually reaches a plateau at which
 290 accuracy can no longer be improved. Therefore, a balance between efficiency and high

291 estimation accuracy can be achieved by including a specific number (121 in this study)
 292 of variables in the model.

293

294 **Fig. 5.** The relationship between the number of input variables and the R (blue line)
 295 and RMSE (red line) values of the estimation models.

296 4.2 Accuracy assessment

297 Figure 6 illustrates the relationship between reference and estimated building
 298 height. Our study confirms the remarkable generalizability of the RF-based building
 299 height model across various cities. Using the least squares regression model, the mean
 300 values of R, RMSE, and MAE were 0.7, 7.6 m, and 6 m, respectively. Meanwhile, the
 301 WLS regression models produced mean values of R, RMSE, and MAE at 0.7, 6.2 m,
 302 and 5.2 m, respectively. The three strongest correlations based on WLS regression
 303 models are obtained for the dataset in Nantong (R=0.87), Beijing (R=0.82) and
 304 Tangshan (R=0.8). Wuhu (4.1 m), Baoding (4.2 m), and Quanzhou (4.5 m) exhibit the
 305 smallest RMSE. The validation results for all samples exhibit a strong statistical
 306 relationship between the estimated and reference building heights (R=0.77 using both
 307 least squares regression and WLS regression models). In the least squares regression
 308 model, the model achieved an uncertainty (RMSE) of 7.4 m and MAE of 5.8 m, in the
 309 WLS regression model the RMSE was 6.1 m and MAE was 5.2 m. Figure 7 shows the

310 distribution of accuracy obtained from two evaluation models. Further results of the
 311 accuracy verification for individual cities can be found in the supplementary Figure S1
 312 and Table S1.

313
 314 **Fig. 6.** Building height validation based on building footprint data, (a) R , (b) $RMSE$,
 315 (c) MAE distribution for each city, and (d) validation results based on all the samples,
 316 white line: one-to-one, red line: ordinary least squares regression, green line: WLS
 317 regression, text in red: regression model, R value and $RMSE$ of the ordinary least
 318 squares model, text in green: regression model, R value and $RMSE$ of the WLS
 319 regression model.

320

321 Fig. 7. The violin plots illustrate the distribution of estimation accuracy for building
 322 heights based on validation samples from 62 cities. (a)-(c) represent the results of
 323 evaluation based on LS regression models, while (d)-(f) represent the results of
 324 evaluation based on WLS regression models. The boxplots inside each violin show the
 325 median, quartiles, and range of estimation accuracy.

326 4.3 Spatial patterns of building height

327 Figure 8 indicates the height distribution of buildings in China in 2020. The results
 328 reveal that megacities in eastern China. More specifically in the Yangtze River Basin
 329 and Delta, the Beijing-Tianjin-Hebei region and Guangzhou-Shenzhen-Hong Kong
 330 regions have the greatest concentrations of high-rise buildings. As would be expected,
 331 large and medium-sized urban centers also have signify taller buildings.

332

333 **Fig. 8.** Spatial distribution of building height in China (10 m spatial resolution), the
334 dataset is freely available on Zenodo, and can be explored in the CNBH-10 m Explorer
335 web app (https://wwanben1994.users.earthengine.app/view/cnbh10_mtest).

336 The CNBH-10m product demonstrably provides accurate representations of
337 building heights in several urban areas, as illustrated in Figure 9. A comparison with
338 high-resolution satellite imagery reveals that the product performs well in estimating
339 point, linear, and clustered arrangements of high-rise buildings and accurately reflects
340 low buildings in older urban areas, such as the historic city of Beijing.

341

342 **Fig. 9.** Sub-samples (10 m spatial resolution) of building height from Beijing, Shanghai,
 343 Guangzhou, Wuhan, Xi'an and Fuzhou.

344 4.4 Regional distribution of building morphology

345 Based on the CNBH 10 m product, the mean building height at city level (Figure
 346 10 a), the high-rise building area (Figure 10 b) and total building volume (Figure 10 c)
 347 are depicted for China. Macau (22.3 m) has the tallest, and Hong Kong (22.1 m) has
 348 the second tallest average building height. The larger metropolitan conurbations in
 349 China, i.e. Beijing, Shanghai, Guangzhou, and Shenzhen have mean building heights
 350 of 12.8 m, 18.0 m, 15.2 m, and 17.9 m, respectively. The distribution of the total area

351 of high-rise buildings (above 24 m) in each city shows that the Beijing-Tianjin-Hebei
 352 region and the Yangtze River Delta region have more high-rise buildings, among which
 353 Shanghai has the most with 209.79 km², followed by Beijing (144.14 km²), Suzhou
 354 (110.99 km²) and Chongqing (106.29 km²). There is a marked difference between the
 355 distribution of accumulated building volume and average building height at city scale.
 356 Cities with greater mean building heights are located especially along the coast and in
 357 central and southwestern China, while the largest building volumes are found in the
 358 most densely populated cities, such as Shanghai (298.4 10⁸ m³), Suzhou (266.8 10⁸ m³)
 359 and Beijing (266.2 10⁸ m³).

360

361 Fig.10. (a) Mean building height (b) High-rise building area (>24 m) and (c)
 362 Accumulated building volume at city level

363 4.5 The relationship between socio-economic parameters and building morphology

364 Using cities as a statistical unit, we compared population and GDP with building
 365 morphology, including mean building height, high-rise building area and accumulated
 366 building volume (Figure 11). The results show that building height generally does not
 367 correlate well with population or GDP, although high-rise building area and building
 368 volume exhibits a strong correlation with two socio-economic parameters. This may be
 369 due to the fact that most of the tall buildings are commercial sites and not located in
 370 residential areas. Population figure actually exhibits the most significant correlation
 371 with the high-rise building area ($R^2=0.66$, $p\text{-value}<0.01$) and building volume ($R^2=0.78$,
 372 $p\text{-value}<0.01$), while GDP also have very strong correlations with these two parameters.

373

374 **Fig. 11.** Scatter plots of multiple socio-economic factors versus mean building height,
 375 high-rise building area and accumulated building volume at city scale. The total
 376 population, GDP was calculated in each city based on gridded population data
 377 (Sorichetta et al. 2015) and GDP product (Chen et al. 2022).

378 5. Discussion

379 5.1 The importance of independent variables on mapping building height

380 The backscattering coefficient is considered to have a strong correlation with
 381 building height, as demonstrated in previous studies (Li et al. 2020c; Yang and Zhao
 382 2022). Accordingly, in this study we incorporate HH, HV polarization data from
 383 PALSAR to improve the accuracy of building height estimation. The complexity of
 384 urban morphology and urban building material differences introduces uncertainties if
 385 using only the backscatter coefficients for large scale and high resolution building
 386 height estimation. So in this study we also applied long time series optical data and
 387 explore application of the shading index. The results demonstrate that the backscatter
 388 coefficient and shading index are the most important variables in the building height
 389 estimation model.

390 In considering the large scale and complex topography of this national-scale study,
 391 information on building location and topography, as well as longitude, latitude, and

392 DEM were used to show that taking account of the relative contributions of these
393 variables to the building height model can improve the generalizability of large-scale
394 building height estimation. When estimating large scale building heights in China,
395 which is more heterogeneous than those in European countries, the multi-window
396 statistical approach used in this study effectively accounts for the model variables, such
397 as shadows for high-rise and low-rise building. The study indicates that it is possible
398 to improve the potential of building height estimation in such complex scenarios.

399 5.2 High accuracy of the building height map

400 In this study, we compared the estimated 10 m building height with existing sets of
401 products, including 30 m (Huang et al. 2022), 500 m (Zhou et al. 2022), and 1000 m
402 building heights (Li et al. 2020a). Figure 12 shows the distribution of building height
403 observation data for six representative cities in China and compares the results across
404 the four building heights. The results indicate that the 10 m building height product
405 provides better detail and more accurately reflects the distribution pattern of building
406 heights compared to other building height product. Furthermore, the 500 m and 1000
407 m building height products fail to reflect building height information at the block scale,
408 thereby demonstrating the superiority of our 10 m building height product.

409

410 **Fig. 12.** Comparison of CNBH-10 m maps with multi-scale building height products
 411 for six Chinese cities

412 Additionally, we randomly selected 20,000 sample points and analyzed the
 413 correlation between the four sets of building height products (Figure 13). To ensure
 414 comparability of building height data across different resolutions, we resample the

415 higher resolution data using the bilinear interpolation method to match the spatial
 416 resolution of the lower resolution data. Our findings show that the 10 m building height
 417 product has a good correlation with the 30 m and 1000 m building height products, with
 418 R values of 0.69 and 0.71, and RMSE values of 5.8 m and 4.4 m, respectively. However,
 419 the findings of this study exhibit a low correlation with the 500 m building height
 420 product, with an R value of only 0.41 and an RMSE value of 12.8 m. This may be due
 421 to the inclusion, in the 500 m building height product, of information on nonbuilding
 422 surfaces such as streets and parking lots (Zhou et al. 2022). This inclusion also explains
 423 the poor correlation between the 500 m and the 30 m and 1000 m building height
 424 products.

425

426 **Fig. 13.** Comparative analysis of multiple floor height products, white line: one-to-one,
 427 red line: ordinary least squares regression, green line: WLS regression, text in red:
 428 regression model, R value and RMSE of the ordinary least squares model, text in green:
 429 regression model, R value and RMSE of the WLS regression model.

430 5.3 Implications and uncertainties

431 Compared with the lower resolution building height products of previous studies
432 (Li et al. 2020a; Li et al. 2020c; Yang and Zhao 2022), the 10 m spatial resolution
433 building height data presented here demonstrates the feasibility of fine-grained urban
434 3D morphological characterization. Moreover, CNBH-10 m products provide
435 potentially important baseline data with a wide range of applications, such as studies of
436 urban microclimate. For example, previous researchers have indicated that the building
437 complexity and the mixture of building types can influence urban ventilation and
438 energy balance, and thus have effect on urban heat accumulation and release (Chun and
439 Guldmann 2014). CNBH-10 m also has great potential in research on urban morphology.
440 Specifically, there are numerous studies on the impact of urban expansion and urban
441 2D landscape patterns on urban ecology and the environment (Li et al. 2011; McDonald
442 et al. 2020). However, the discontinuity and high economic cost of urban 3D data
443 collection have made it difficult to quantify these impacts in cities. Together with the
444 3D building morphology metrics proposed in previous studies (Guo et al. 2021; Wu et
445 al. 2017), CNBH10 m has great potential to fill this gap.

446 Despite these promising results, several limitations of the methodology need to be
447 acknowledged. Due to the complex 3D structure and high degree of heterogeneity of
448 cities, there are several uncertainties in the estimation of building height and these need
449 to be carefully taken into account when applying the methodology. For example,
450 additional shadows caused by trees and overpasses between buildings may affect the
451 estimation of building height, future efforts to mitigate these uncertainties can be
452 pursued through the utilization of multi-angle remote sensing techniques or the
453 acquisition of higher-resolution satellite imagery (Kadhim and Mourshed 2017; Liu et
454 al. 2020; Tripathy et al. 2022). The data resampling method used in the study may also
455 have an impact on the results of the building height estimation. Here, the WSF dataset
456 was used as the base map for building distribution, and a masking process was applied
457 to the final CNBH-10m product. The accuracy of the base map has a significant

458 influence on the accuracy of the building height product, especially for the building
459 volume estimation. Future research could explore the combination of multiple building
460 distribution products, such as GHS-BUILT-S2 (Corbane et al. 2021), to improve the
461 accuracy. Due to the use of a pixel-based method for estimating building height, the
462 final results of building height estimation exhibited some noise. Moreover, the multi-
463 window approach used for processing input variables resulted in some smoothing
464 effects in the building height products. To enhance the accuracy of building height
465 estimation, future studies may consider utilizing object-based methods or employing
466 post-processing techniques on building height products, in conjunction with more
467 precise building boundaries such as vector boundaries of individual buildings
468 (Milojevic-Dupont et al. 2023). The use of three-year remote sensing imagery for
469 building height inversion in this study may also introduce uncertainties in the results
470 due to rapid urban development in China. Moreover, due to computational limitations
471 and mapping efficiency, this study only used the RF model for building height
472 estimation and comparison, while further refinements may be achieved through deep
473 learning methods. Although nighttime lighting and population data are also used as
474 variables for building height estimation in the study, they do not contribute well to the
475 building height estimation model, which is likely due to the low spatial resolution of
476 these data..

477 **6. Conclusion**

478 This study demonstrates the potential of using earth observation data for national-
479 scale building height estimation and establishes a high degree of accuracy of simulated
480 building height based on RF regression modeling. Specifically, a total of 519 different
481 feature variables were derived from earth observation data collected in all-weather
482 conditions, and building heights were analyzed based on multitemporal, multispectral,
483 and multiscale geospatial big data. The shading index, the backscattering coefficient,
484 and the location of the building are the most significant contributors to the China-wide
485 building height estimation model which has the potential for universality,

486 transferability and reliability in terms of accuracy. Estimated and observed building
487 heights exhibit R, RMSE and MAE values of 0.77, 6.1 m and 5.2 m respectively. In
488 summary, the method and outputs indicate the potential of multi-source, multi-time,
489 multi-window algorithms and cloud-based computing platforms for large-scale, refined
490 building height mapping. The CNBH-10 m product can be applied to a wide range of
491 urban process studies, such as urban climate, energy consumption and population
492 estimates. The CNBH-10 m product is fully open source and freely available
493 (<https://zenodo.org/record/7064268#.YxtVAuxBz0p>).

494 **Declaration of Competing Interest**

495 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal
496 relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

497 **Acknowledgements**

498 This research was supported by the National Key Research and Development Project
499 of China (grant no. 2021YFE0193100, 2018YFD0900806), European Union's Horizon
500 2020 research and innovation program (grant no. 821016) and China Scholarship
501 Council (grant no. 202106100112).

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